

Supplementary Material

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1 Methods

1.1 Rotational elastography - Calculating array derived rotations

It follows from the main text (equations 1-8) that the wave speed c_s at angular frequency ω can be calculated from the local ratio of translational and rotational motion.

In magnetic resonance elastography with a harmonic excitation, this signifies that the only numerical derivatives required to retrieve local wavespeed estimates are the first spatial derivatives in x, y, z , which required to retrieve the rotation of the particle velocity:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \phi_x \\ \phi_y \\ \phi_z \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_x \\ \partial_y \\ \partial_z \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ u_z \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_y u_z - \partial_z u_y \\ \partial_z u_x - \partial_x u_z \\ \partial_x u_y - \partial_y u_x \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

1.2 (Auto-) Phase conjugation

To increase signal-to-noise I multiply each complex particle velocity value with its complex conjugate. This is equivalent to an autocorrelation in the time domain. A similar processing in the time domain has been employed by [1] to retrieve an energy tomography in ultrasound elastography. In contrast with that approach, the phase conjugation here does not prevent quantitative wave speed measurements, because Eq. (1) is a local solution and the frequency ω is known. Eq. (1) still holds for $\sqrt{(\tilde{U}_x \tilde{U}_x^*) / (\tilde{\Phi}_y \tilde{\Phi}_y^*)}$. For the figure in the main text, two iterations of this fourier autocorrelation equivalent were employed.

1.3 Time-Reversal, cross-correlation, phase conjugation, and diffuse fields

The concept of a numerical Time-Reversal Mirror and wave interferometry are closely linked through the cross-correlation of diffuse wave fields [2],[3] [4–6]. In short, a new signal is created from correlation of the measured diffuse signals. This was pioneered by Claerbout [7] and continued in acoustics [8], seismic imaging [9], helioseismology [10], ultrasound [11], earthquake seismology [12], ocean acoustics [13] and medical imaging [14]. If the signals of a diffuse field at two receivers are cross-correlated, the Green's function between those two receivers can be retrieved. For non-perfectly diffuse fields higher orders of correlation have been proposed [15]. If the signal at one receiver is cross-correlated with the signals at all the other receivers in a dense array, a virtual wave-field which converges towards, focuses at, and radiates again away from the first receiver is created. This is called the focal spot method [14] [16]. In the frequency domain, a time-reversal becomes a phase conjugation and the correlation of a field with its time reverse becomes a multiplication of the field with its phase conjugated field [17]. While no Time-reversal focal spot will be created from a monochromatic field, digital phase conjugation is applied in optics, also to enhance focus [18].

1.3.1 Time-reversal and Autocorrelation

Cross-correlation in interferometry is performed on time-domain signals [19]. The seismology community has been using a frequency domain method, spatial auto-correlation (SPAC) since [20]. Interferometry and SPAC theories are consistent, which has been outlined by [21, 22]. The time integral of the normalized spatial correlation of a random field allows Green's function retrieval [23]. Hence, in a homogeneous part of the medium the time-integral of the zero-time lag correlation of

a measurement point and its neighbors retrieves the same focal spot as would the temporal cross-correlation of said points with its neighbours. An autocorrelation property is employed in passive elastography [14, 24] and reverberant elastography [25]. While the first take a time-reversal approach for the derivation, and the latter do not, the methods are consistent and share the same interferometric principles for diffuse fields [26]. For the present data I applied a spatial autocorrelation in a stencil comprising all directly neighbouring voxels for each voxel of the field of view. Note, that even for non-perfectly diffuse fields this should enhance SNR [27].

1.3.2 3D Phase conjugaison

The above mentioned time-domain focal spot method achieves a focal spot at each measurement location of a dense array through correlation of said spot with the surrounding array. In short, from a broadband diffuse field, the correlation retrieves a spherical wavefront that converges at negative times, focuses on the focal spot at time 0, and diverges at positive times. Because this can be done for many sensor locations, one spatially diffuse field can result in the retrieval of one spatially coherent (spherical) wave-field for each sensor location, a computationally expensive task. In the case of the experimental data of [28, 29] used in this paper, we have a complex harmonic field. The harmonic equivalent of cross-correlation is multiplication with the phase conjugate (indeed, in seismology cross-correlation are often performed as a multiplication with the phase conjugate frequency per frequency in the fourier domain for computational reasons). This leads to the main text's formula $c_s = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\mathbf{r}_0=1}^n \frac{(i\omega \tilde{U}(r|\mathbf{r}_0)_x / \tilde{\Phi}(r|\mathbf{r}_0)_y)}{-2 \cos(\theta)}$, where $\tilde{U}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)^{PC} = \tilde{U}(\mathbf{r}_0)\tilde{U}(\mathbf{r})^*$ and n is the number of voxels in the array or chosen window in the array. For the presented results, the window is given by $r \in r_0 \pm 5/15 dr$ with $dr=[1.8, 1.8, 1.5]$ mm.

Figure 1: Interferometric processing results: Left: Shear wave tomography using $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$ and iterative phase conjugation. Middle: Shear wave tomography using $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$ and iterative phase conjugation. Right: Combined shear wave tomography using both $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$ and $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$ with iterative phase conjugation.

1.4 Processing flow

The data input to the processing workflow is \tilde{U} , the complex three component motion data for a 70Hz excitation, as provided by [29]. The left panel of the figure of the main text is described by the following workflow:

For the right panel, the 3D phase conjugation of each voxel with all voxels in a window $r \in r_0 \pm 11 dr$ with $dr=[1.8, 1.8, 1.5]$ mm is performed before the above workflow. The shear wave speed value at each voxel is then the average of all windows containing that voxel and the last 3D Gaussian filter in the flow diagram is removed. $c_s = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{r_0=1}^N \frac{i\omega\tilde{U}_x^{PC}(r|r_0)/\tilde{\Phi}_y^{PC}(r|r_0)}{-2 \cos(\theta)}$. As mentioned in the main text, the shown tomography is a result from further averaging c_s derived from $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$: $c_s = \frac{1}{2N} (\sum_{r_0=1}^N \frac{i\omega\tilde{U}_x^{PC}(r|r_0)/\tilde{\Phi}_y^{PC}(r|r_0)}{-2 \cos(\theta)} + \sum_{r_0=1}^N \frac{i\omega\tilde{U}_y^{PC}(r|r_0)/\tilde{\Phi}_x^{PC}(r|r_0)}{2 \cos(\theta)})$. The results for the contributions of the individual polarizations are shown below.

2 Synthetic Noise Addition

Figure 2: Real part of motion fields with 50%RMS added noise (see main manuscript). Top: Translational Motions; Bottom: Rotational Motions, derived via 1 voxel central finite difference stencil)

Figure 3: Imaginary part of motion fields with 50%RMS added noise (see main manuscript). Top: Translational Motions; Bottom: Rotational Motions, derived via 1 voxel central finite difference stencil)

Figure 4: Shear modulus tomography through Rotational Elastography of the experimental brain phantom data of [29] at 70 Hz, but with added noise (standard deviation 50 % RMS). A slice in $x - y$ is shown. Top: Rotational elastography using different polarizations $\tilde{U}_{x/y}$ and $\tilde{\Phi}_{y/x}$. The third panel is the average of the first two. Middle: Interferometric processing in 3D through Phase conjugation and subsequent rotational elastography on the same polarizations as above, with a phase conjugation in a 5 voxel 3D window. Bottom: Same as above with phase conjugation in a 15 voxel 3D window. The diameter of the three stiff inclusions is given as 18,12 and 4 mm by [28]. The smallest inclusion is invisible in MRI, subzone, and reverberant elastography [28]. Nominal background elasticity is 3.34 ± 0.04 kPa and inclusion elasticity is 8.15 ± 0.05 kPa [28]. The insert sketches the slice orientation in a phantom, and the indicated translational and rotational motion vectors illustrate that each voxel/pixel is the result of leveraging six degrees-of-freedom.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	0	12.6 ± 6.5	1.9	31.1	13.9	0.96	1.1	0.83
BG 1	–	0	2.3 ± 0.33	7.0	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	0	8.2 ± 2.5	3.2	11.4	17.8	0.97	0.64	0.42
BG 2	–	0	3.1 ± 0.45	6.9	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	0	4.1 ± 0.51	8.1	4.3	17.1	0.88	0.23	0.15
BG 3	–	0	3.1 ± 0.25	12.1	–	–	–	–	–

Table 1: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for the average of $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$; $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	0	8.2 ± 3.5	2.3	11.7	13.6	0.96	0.94	0.62
BG 1	–	0	2.7 ± 0.47	5.8	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	0	7.9 ± 2.1	3.7	40.9	21.4	0.97	0.66	0.44
BG 2	–	0	2.7 ± 0.13	21.5	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	0	7.8 ± 1.1	7.4	42.7	33.4	0.88	0.46	0.22
BG 3	–	0	2.6 ± 0.12	22.0	–	–	–	–	–

Table 2: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	0	17.0 ± 10.4	1.6	38.3	12.4	0.94	1.1	0.88
BG 1	–	0	1.9 ± 0.39	4.8	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	0	8.4 ± 3.5	2.4	5.6	11.6	0.80	0.62	0.40
BG 2	–	0	3.4 ± 0.88	3.9	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	0	0.52 ± 0.19	2.8	7.1	38.4	0.88	0.86	0.59
BG 3	–	0	3.5 ± 0.42	8.3	–	–	–	–	–

Table 3: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	0	7.0 ± 2.3	3.0	3.5	14.0	0.77	1.4	0.71
BG 1	50	0	2.9 ± 1.2	2.4	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	0	6.9 ± 1.6	4.3	5.6	18.9	0.86	0.84	0.34
BG 2	50	0	3.3 ± 0.65	5.0	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	0	4.3 ± 0.63	6.8	1.3	5.4	0.59	0.53	0.31
BG 3	50	0	3.4 ± 0.70	4.8	–	–	–	–	–

Table 4: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for the average of $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$; $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	0	7.0 ± 3.3	2.1	1.7	4.6	0.72	0.80	0.62
BG 1	50	0	3.4 ± 2.2	1.6	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	0	7.1 ± 1.3	5.4	19.8	26.2	0.97	0.69	0.43
BG 2	50	0	2.8 ± 0.21	13.0	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	0	5.9 ± 1.5	3.8	10.6	18.8	0.88	0.49	0.32
BG 3	50	0	2.6 ± 0.31	8.5	–	–	–	–	–

Table 5: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	0	7.0 ± 3.1	2.2	4.2	11.9	0.76	1.7	0.91
BG 1	50	0	2.4 ± 1.1	2.1	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	0	6.7 ± 2.4	2.8	2.4	7.9	0.57	0.48	0.16
BG 2	50	0	3.7 ± 1.2	3.0	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	0	2.6 ± 0.69	3.8	1.3	7.5	0.79	1.1	0.97
BG 3	50	0	4.1 ± 1.1	3.6	–	–	–	–	–

Table 6: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	5	6.5 ± 1.8	3.7	7.3	20.7	0.94	1.1	0.89
BG 1	–	5	2.1 ± 0.59	3.6	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	5	4.4 ± 1.5	2.8	7.6	15.6	0.86	0.57	0.25
BG 2	–	5	1.6 ± 0.36	4.5	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	5	5.4 ± 2.4	2.3	8.4	12.8	0.88	0.16	0.05
BG 3	–	5	1.9 ± 0.42	4.4	–	–	–	–	–

Table 7: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for the average of $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$; $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	5	7.6 ± 3.1	2.5	7.1	16.6	0.88	1.5	0.83
BG 1	–	5	1.7 ± 0.83	2.1	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	5	3.4 ± 2.2	1.6	2.8	4.7	0.57	1.5	0.02
BG 2	–	5	1.2 ± 0.78	1.6	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	5	0.04 ± 0.03	1.0	2.0	17.6	0.88	1.1	0.87
BG 3	–	5	1.8 ± 0.88	2.0	–	–	–	–	–

Table 8: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	5	5.3 ± 1.1	4.7	5.0	19.6	0.86	1.7	1.2
BG 1	–	5	2.6 ± 0.55	4.6	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	5	5.4 ± 1.1	5.1	27.3	26.0	0.97	0.81	0.43
BG 2	–	5	2.0 ± 0.12	16.2	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	5	10.8 ± 4.7	2.3	181.7	16.9	0.88	0.24	0.07
BG 3	–	5	1.9 ± 0.05	40.0	–	–	–	–	–

Table 9: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	5	4.2 ± 1.0	4.2	5.3	18.4	0.88	1.9	0.85
BG 1	50	5	2.0 ± 0.42	4.8	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	5	4.5 ± 1.4	3.1	11.2	17.8	0.97	0.61	0.37
BG 2	50	5	1.6 ± 0.26	6.3	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	5	2.4 ± 0.36	6.6	4.3	17.0	0.88	0.25	0.15
BG 3	50	5	1.6 ± 0.18	9.2	–	–	–	–	–

Table 10: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for the average of $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$; $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	5	3.8 ± 1.4	2.6	4.9	10.8	0.76	1.8	0.18
BG 1	50	5	1.8 ± 0.40	4.5	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	5	3.5 ± 1.5	2.3	4.3	11.8	0.74	0.50	0.28
BG 2	50	5	1.3 ± 0.50	2.5	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	5	1.1 ± 0.14	8.3	0.92	3.4	0.59	1.0	0.98
BG 3	50	5	1.5 ± 0.36	4.1	–	–	–	–	–

Table 11: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	5	4.7 ± 1.2	3.8	4.1	16.0	0.79	1.8	1.1
BG 1	50	5	2.2 ± 0.60	3.7	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	5	5.6 ± 1.7	3.3	19.5	19.4	0.97	0.80	0.42
BG 2	50	5	2.0 ± 0.18	10.6	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	5	3.7 ± 0.69	5.4	17.4	23.1	0.88	0.29	0.16
BG 3	50	5	1.8 ± 0.11	17.1	–	–	–	–	–

Table 12: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	15	5.5 ± 0.60	9.1	12.5	34.0	0.98	1.2	0.78
BG 1	–	15	2.2 ± 0.26	8.4	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	15	3.2 ± 0.52	6.2	8.5	25.1	0.97	0.68	0.35
BG 2	–	15	1.5 ± 0.20	7.9	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	15	2.7 ± 0.40	6.8	9.7	23.1	0.88	0.24	0.10
BG 3	–	15	1.6 ± 0.11	13.9	–	–	–	–	–

Table 13: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for the average of $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y ; \tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	15	5.3 ± 1.4	3.8	10.3	21.5	0.98	0.94	0.56
BG 1	–	15	1.8 ± 0.34	5.2	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	15	3.4 ± 0.79	4.3	6.3	23.4	0.97	0.67	0.34
BG 2	–	15	0.98 ± 0.38	2.6	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	15	0.37 ± 0.15	2.5	3.3	23.8	0.88	0.92	0.28
BG 3	–	15	1.1 ± 0.22	5.0	–	–	–	–	–

Table 14: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	15	5.7 ± 0.93	6.2	10.5	26.2	0.98	1.4	0.90
BG 1	–	15	2.6 ± 0.30	8.9	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	15	3.0 ± 0.36	8.5	32.3	22.7	0.97	0.68	0.38
BG 2	–	15	2.1 ± 0.03	72.5	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	15	5.1 ± 0.85	6.0	93.7	27.7	0.88	0.29	0.12
BG 3	–	15	2.1 ± 0.03	66.6	–	–	–	–	–

Table 15: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	15	4.8 ± 0.59	8.2	10.7	30.4	0.98	1.2	0.65
BG 1	50	15	2.2 ± 0.24	9.3	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	15	3.0 ± 0.42	7.1	5.3	22.7	0.91	0.89	0.41
BG 2	50	15	1.7 ± 0.24	7.3	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	15	2.5 ± 0.20	12.8	3.6	22.1	0.88	0.36	0.18
BG 3	50	15	1.8 ± 0.19	9.5	–	–	–	–	–

Table 16: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for the average of $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$; $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	15	4.3 ± 1.2	3.5	10.0	17.8	0.98	–	–
BG 1	50	15	1.8 ± 0.25	7.4	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	15	3.0 ± 0.60	5.0	3.4	18.7	0.91	0.91	0.38
BG 2	50	15	1.4 ± 0.47	2.9	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	15	1.4 ± 0.15	9.8	0.45	-9.1	0.71	1.1	0.04
BG 3	50	15	1.6 ± 0.38	4.2	–	–	–	–	–

Table 17: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	50	15	5.3 ± 0.78	6.8	7.6	25.9	0.98	1.4	0.84
BG 1	50	15	2.6 ± 0.35	7.5	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	15	3.0 ± 0.33	9.0	39.3	23.7	0.97	0.76	0.45
BG 2	50	15	2.1 ± 0.02	87.9	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	15	3.6 ± 0.44	8.3	73.4	28.2	0.88	0.56	0.20
BG 3	50	15	2.1 ± 0.02	96.9	–	–	–	–	–

Table 18: Metrics for the ROIS from the main manuscript for $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$.

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